

Advances in Electrospun Nanofibers for Scar Removal and Tissue Regeneration

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Abstract

Nanotechnology has emerged as a promising approach for wound healing and scar removal, offering unique solutions to promote tissue regeneration and reduce scarring. Electrospun nanofibers have gained significant attention due to their ability to mimic the extracellular matrix and provide an ideal environment for cell adhesion, proliferation, and differentiation. This comprehensive review explores the recent advances in electrospinning-related/-based nanotechnology for scar management, focusing on the fabrication techniques, therapeutic applications, and safety considerations. Various electrospinning methods, including needle-based, needleless, melt, emulsion, and solution electrospinning, are discussed via highlighting their advantages and limitations. The incorporation of therapeutic agents, such as drugs, growth factors, and stem cells, into electrospun nanofibers has shown promise in promoting wound healing, and reducing scar formation. However, the biocompatibility and safety of these nanomaterials remain a concern, necessitating rigorous research to ensure their long-term safety, and efficacy. The potential toxicity, biodistribution, immune response, and the regulatory aspects of nanotechnology-based scar treatments are critically examined. Despite the challenges, the future perspectives of electrospun nanotechnology in scar management are promising, with the potential to revolutionize wound care and improve patient outcomes. Further research and development in this field are essential to transform these innovative approaches into clinical practice.

Keywords

Electrospun nanofibers, Wound healing, Scar management, Nanotechnology, Tissue regeneration

1. Introduction

Nanotechnology has been increasingly used in medicine, including scar removal [1]. Scar removal is a complex process that involves the regeneration of damaged skin tissue, and nanotechnology offers unique solutions to this problem [2]. One promising application of the nanotechnology in scar removal is the use of nanofibers [3]. Nanofibers are tiny fibres with diameters in the nm range, which can be produced from various materials such as polymers, ceramics, and metals [4]. These fibres can be used to create scaffolds that support the growth

of new skin tissue [5]. Nanofibers can also be loaded with drugs or growth factors to promote tissue regeneration and reduce scarring [6]. Another application of nanotechnology in scar removal is using nanocarriers for drug delivery [7]. Nanocarriers are tiny particles that can be loaded with drugs, and can be targeted to specific areas of the body [8]. In scar removal, nanocarriers can deliver drugs or growth factors directly to the site of the scar, promoting tissue regeneration and reducing scarring [2]. Nanotechnology has also been used to develop new materials for skin regeneration [9]. Our previous paper (its better to say “In a previous study...”) thoroughly discusses the nano transdermal delivery systems that aimed to enhance skin mechanisms. It explores the use of nano transdermal delivery systems for the administration?? (the meaning is still not clear) of herbal extracts, focusing on their potential in dermatological treatments and skin care [10].

While many of these applications are still in experimental stage/level, they offer exciting possibilities for the future of scar removal and skin repair [11]. As the research and development continues, the nanotechnology will provide more effective and efficient solutions for the fields of scar removal, and skin regeneration.

2. Understanding the Scar Formation and Wound Healing: A Molecular Perspective

Scar formation is a complex process that involves a series of molecular and cellular events during wound healing. The initial phase of the wound healing is the inflammatory phase, during which the damaged tissues release pro-inflammatory cytokines and growth factors. This results in the recruitment of immune cells, such as neutrophils and macrophages towards the wound site [12]. During the subsequent proliferative phase, fibroblasts migrate to the wound site, and start to synthesize extracellular matrix (ECM) proteins, such as collagen and fibronectin. This is accompanied by the formation of tissue granulation, which provides a scaffold for the growth of the new tissue [13]. Finally, during the remodelling phase, the ECM is reorganized, and then degraded to form a scar [14]. The balance between the ECM synthesis and degradation during this phase is critical in determining the quality of the new scar tissue [15]. Here, several molecular pathways, which play important roles in scar formation and wound healing, have been identified. For example, the transforming growth factor-beta (TGF- β) signalling is critical in regulating the ECM synthesis during the proliferative phase [16]. In addition, the Wnt?? (what does it mean? Abbreviation of sth.?) signalling pathway has been implicated in both regulating cell proliferation and differentiation during wound healing [17].

Understanding the molecular mechanisms that underlies the scar formation and wound healing is essential for the development of new therapies in both scar removal and tissue regeneration. By targeting specific molecular pathways, it may be possible to promote tissue regeneration while reducing the scar formation.

The human skin is the body's largest organ, which serves as a protective barrier against the external environment that prevents dehydration and injuries. When the skin is injured, a sequence of events begins immediately. The cutaneous wound repair consists of several phases including the overlapping that involves the inflammatory response, the formation of tissue granulation that involves the angiogenesis and re-epithelialization, and the matrix remodelling [18,19]. Fig. 1 illustrates the three fundamental phases of wound healing.

Fig. 1. The fundamental phases of wound healing

The integumental injuries refer to outer wounds, while inner or closed wounds involve injuries or ruptures of inner organs and tissues with intact skin. Skin wounds can be closed by either regeneration or repair. The regeneration involves the specific replacement of the tissue, such as superficial epidermis, mucosa, or fetal skin, whereas the repair is an unspecific form of healing that involves fibrosis and scar formation. Unfortunately, the scar formation is the predominant form of healing in adult skin wounds [20,21]. The interplay between cells, growth factors, and cytokines leads to skin closure after an injury. Although disruptions in this delicate balance can occur, recent findings suggest that the absence of a particular cell type or mediator can be compensated by other factors involved in wound healing, allowing the repair process to proceed [22].

2.1. Wound Healing Phases

The process of wound healing involves four interdependent and interrelated phases of hemostasis, inflammation, proliferation, and tissue remodelling or resolution. These phases are highly integrated and overlap each other [23]. For a successful wound healing to occur, these phases and their physiological functions must take place in a specific order, with precise timing, and for a specific duration with optimal intensity [24]. Table 1 shows the wound healing phases and their timeframes.

Table 1. Wound healing phases [25,26]

Phase	Timeframe	Description
Hemostasis	0-1 day	This phase occurs immediately after injury and lasts up to a day. It is characterized by vasoconstriction, platelet aggregation, and clot formation to stop bleeding and establish a stable wound environment.

Inflammatory	0-4 days	It begins immediately after injury and lasts up to 4 days. Inflammation is characterized by vasoconstriction, clot formation, and infiltration of immune cells to remove debris and prevent infection.
Proliferative	4-21 days	Duration from day 4 to day 21 after injury. This phase is marked by angiogenesis, fibroblast proliferation, collagen synthesis, and wound contraction.
Remodelling	21 days - 2 years	It can last up to 2 years after injury. During this phase, the wound undergoes remodelling and maturation, with collagen fibres realigning and scar tissue forming. The scar tissue gradually becomes stronger but will never regain the strength of uninjured tissue.

During the hemostasis phase, blood vessels constrict to reduce blood loss, and platelets aggregate to form a clot. In the inflammation phase, immune cells, such as neutrophils and macrophages, are recruited towards the wound site to clear debris and pathogens. Growth factors and cytokines are also released during this phase, to stimulate cell proliferation and angiogenesis. The proliferation phase is characterized by the migration and proliferation of fibroblasts and keratinocytes, leading to the formation of tissue granulation and re-epithelialization of the wound. During the tissue remodelling or the resolution phase, the extracellular matrix is reorganized, and then is degraded, resulting in scar formation or tissue regeneration, depending on the injury's extent, and the wound's location. Fibroblasts, originating from the mesenchymal cells, are vital in wound healing due to producing new extracellular matrix components. The matrix production results in the restoration of tissue homeostasis [27]. The tissue remodelling phase is the final stage of wound healing and can last up to one year after the injury. During this phase, the collagenase enzymes secreted by fibroblasts, macrophages, and neutrophils break down the collagen molecules, leading to their degradation [28]. As collagen is broken down during the tissue remodelling phase, it is gradually replaced by the Type I collagen. This replacement increases the tensile strength of the new tissue over time [14]. Here, the collagen fibres in wound tissue are thinner than those of normal dermal collagen. Over time, these thinner fibres will thicken and organize themselves along the stress lines of the injury. However, the resulting scar tissue will never be as muscular as the normal tissue that preceded it [25,29,30]. Several studies have indicated that variations in inflammation during the wound-healing process are strongly linked to the extent of scar tissue formation [31]. The fetal wound healing is an example of the correlation between the inflammation and the scar tissue formation. Fetal wounds are lack of typical inflammatory markers, and are known to be "scarless" up to a certain age [14]. In adult wound healing, polymorphonuclear leukocytes are the first immune cells recruited towards the wound site, followed by the macrophages and lymphocytes. In contrast, the fetal wounds are lack of polymorphonuclear leukocytes, and as the healing process progresses, fetal macrophages enter the wound site in smaller numbers than those found in adults [2]. The lack of an inflammatory response in fetal wounds may be due to a deficiency in appropriate signalling, and the immature state of fetal inflammatory cell populations. In non-healing wounds, the failure in transition from the inflammatory phase to the proliferative phase can result in abnormal wound repair.

2.2.Factors Affecting the Wound Healing

Several factors, including age, underlying medical conditions, medications, nutrition, and the lifestyle-related factors can affect the wound healing. For example, older adults may experience delayed wound healing due to reduced cell proliferation, and decreased growth factor

production. The diabetes, hypertension, and other chronic diseases can also impair wound healing by negatively affecting both the blood flow and immune functions [32]. Medications, such as nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), can impair wound healing by reducing the inflammatory response, and by inhibiting the production of growth factors [33]. Nutritional deficiencies, such as vitamin C deficiency, can impair wound healing by affecting the collagen synthesis and angiogenesis [21]. The lifestyle-related factors, such as smoking and alcohol consumption, can also impair wound healing by reducing both the blood flow and oxygen delivery towards the wound site [32]. In short, the impaired wound healing can have significant consequences, such as chronic wounds, infection, and scarring. The chronic wounds, such as pressure ulcers and diabetic foot ulcers, can result from impaired wound healing due to underlying medical conditions and/or other factors [34]. Infections can also occur when the inflammatory response is inadequate or when the wound is contaminated with bacteria. The scarring can result from excessive collagen deposition during tissue remodelling, leading to hypertrophic or keloid scars [26].

The wound-healing process is a series of complex events that involves the coordinated effort of cells, growth factors, cytokines, and extracellular matrix components. Numerous factors can badly influence the wound healing, leading to impaired or improper tissue repair.

3. Scar Formation

Scarring is a significant burden on healthcare systems worldwide, and has prompted extensive research to prevent and reduce its occurrence [35,36]. A fully mature scar comprises Type I collagen [37]. In a scar tissue, Type I collagen is arranged in bundles parallel to the skin surface, unlike the non-parallel arrangement in normal skin [38]. The epidermal basement membrane in a scar tissue is flatter than normal skin since it lacks the rete pegs that usually penetrate the dermis [9]. The scar tissue is also lack of other typical dermal structures, such as hair follicles or sweat glands [39,40]. As the scar tissue matures, the concentration of fibroblasts within the tissue decreases. The scar tissue also has less elastin in its extracellular matrix that contributes to the loss of tensile strength and increases the likelihood of re-injury than that of a healthy tissue [41]. The degree of fibrosis after an injury varies depending on the organ or the affected tissue. If the molecular regulation of the tissue remodelling phase of wound healing is inefficient or disrupted, problematic scars such as hypertrophic scars or keloids can develop. Hypertrophic scars, such as burns, usually arise after a surgery or a trauma [42]. Scars are formed during wound healing and their formation involves four phases: hemostasis, inflammation, proliferation, and tissue remodelling. The tissue remodelling phase is the final stage of wound healing, during which the collagen is broken down and is replaced by Type I collagen. The parallel arrangement of these collagen fibres, reduces the tensile strength, and the absence of typical dermal structures such as hair follicles and sweat glands characterizes a scar tissue.

3.1. Scar Types

3.1.1. Acne Scars

Acne scarring is a common concern among patients seeking facial rejuvenation. This complexity necessitates a comprehensive evaluation of each patient's unique scar profile to develop a tailored treatment plan [43]. Various treatment modalities, including chemical peels, microneedling, laser resurfacing, and dermal fillers have shown promising results in addressing

different types of acne scars [44]. The selection of an appropriate treatment or combination of treatments depends on factors such as the scar type, severity, skin type, and the patient's preferences. While acne and its resulting scars typically occur in one's teenage or early adulthood, patients may request treatment for acne scarring at any age [43]. The three primary categories of acne scars are classified as the ice pick, rolling, and the boxcar, with the optimal treatment modality potentially varying for each subtype [45]. However, most patients have a combination of these subtypes, making the determination of the optimal treatment approach more challenging. One of the primary obstacles in developing a standardized approach for treating acne scars is the lack of high-quality studies since the existing studies are often small, biased, and are lack of uniform baseline variables and outcomes or have a limited follow-up period [46]. Fig. 2 illustrates the type of scars.

Fig. 2. Type of scars

Ice Pick Scars

The Ice Pick scars are narrow and deep scars that resemble the puncture made by an ice pick. Due to their depth, they can be more challenging to treat than either rolling or boxcar scars. However, some treatment options can provide excellent results. The punch excision is an effective treatment for the ice pick scars. Although this procedure involves creating a new scar, the scars from the punch excision can often heal to barely noticeable [47]. here, the scars should be at least 4-5 mm apart to be simultaneously treated. If the scars are too close to each other, the skin surface will experience too much tension that can hinder the optimal healing. In cases where scars are located within 4-5 mm away of one another, it is best to wait for 4 weeks between treatments to achieve the best long-term results [45].

Rolling Scars

The rolling scars are broad depressions in the skin with sloping edges, that create a rolling or wave-like appearances. They are typically caused by a damage beneath the skin surface, which can cause the subcutaneous tissue to adhere to the deeper structures. As a result, the skin surface appears uneven and dimpled. The rolling scars can be treated with several modalities, including the micro-needling and the laser resurfacing. These treatments can help to break up the underlying fibrous tissue, to stimulate collagen production, and to promote smoother skin

texture. However, the ideal treatment approach may vary based on the individual's skin type and the scar's severity [48].

Boxcar Scars

The boxcar scars are angular or rectangular-shaped depressions in the skin with well-defined edges. They are typically wider than the Ice Pick scars, and also have a flat base. These scars are caused by the destruction of collagen, resulting in a depression in the skin. The ideal treatment approach for the boxcar scars may vary depending on the severity of the scarring, but commonly used treatments include the punch excision, the dermal fillers, and the laser resurfacing. The punch excision involves the surgical removal of the scar, and then suturing the surrounding skin together, with the help of dermal fillers to lift the scar, and to create a smoother skin surface. The laser resurfacing can both help to promote collagen production, and to improve the overall appearance of the skin [49,50].

Erythematous Scars

The erythematous scars are pink or red in colour, and are caused by excess blood flow to the scar tissue. They are typically raised, thick, and itchy, and can be caused by various factors, including acne, surgery or injury. The treatment options for such scars include the application of topical creams, silicone sheets or gels, and the laser therapy. The topical creams and silicone sheets or gels can both help to reduce the redness and inflammation while promoting healing. The laser therapy can both help to reduce the scar's size, and to stimulate collagen production, resulting in a smoother and a less noticeable scar. The ideal treatment approach may vary depending on the severity, and the cause of the scar [51].

3.1.2. Surgical Scars

Treating surgical scars requires consideration of various factors, such as the timing of interventions, and the specific type of the scar. Scars can be erythematous, raised, or depressed and may need different treatments. Patients may inquire about the benefits of silicone gel sheeting in the immediate aftermath of the surgery, but evidence for its effectiveness is weak, and is susceptible to bias. Physicians must thoroughly understand scar management techniques, including the topical treatments, injections, surgery, and the laser therapy to provide optimal patient care. Early intervention and wound care can also improve the scar outcomes [52].

Hypertrophic Scars

Hypertrophic scars are raised, red, and thick scars that form due to an overproduction of collagen during healing. They are common after a surgery, burns, or trauma, and can cause physical and emotional discomfort for patients. Treatment options for hypertrophic scars include the topical creams, corticosteroid injections, silicone sheets or gels, the laser therapy, and surgery. Surgery may be considered if other treatments are ineffective, but it carries a risk of recurrence or further scarring. A combination of these treatments may be applied to achieve the best results for each patient [53].

Atrophic Scars

The atrophic surgical scars are characterized by depression or indentation in the skin, and present different challenges than that of the hypertrophic scars. They can be more difficult to treat, and may require a tailored approach. One treatment option for the atrophic surgical scars

is the application of fractional laser therapy. This therapy involves using either non-ablative or fully ablative lasers to target the scar tissue, to stimulate collagen production, and to improve the scar's colour, texture, thickness, and the patient's satisfaction. Other treatments for the atrophic surgical scars may include the application of dermal fillers, micro-needling or the surgical scar revision. The choice of treatment depends on the severity, and the location of the scar, as well as the patient's skin type and his/her medical history. Physicians must have a thorough understanding of the scar management techniques to provide the optimal care for their patients with atrophic surgical scars [54–56].

4. Current Scar Treatments

There are various options for scar treatment, depending on the type and the severity of the scar. The topical treatments such as creams, gels, and silicone sheets can help to improve the appearance of scars by reducing redness, flattening the scar, and improving its texture [51]. Injections of corticosteroids can treat both the hypertrophic and keloid scars by reducing inflammation, and by flattening the scar [57]. The surgical excision is also a standard treatment for the hypertrophic and keloid scars, while the laser therapy can improve the scars' appearance, and can stimulate the collagen production [37]. The cryotherapy involves freezing the scar tissue to reduce the inflammation and to flatten the scar [38]. The pressure therapy involves applying pressure to the scar by using a special bandage or dressing to reduce inflammation, and to flatten the scar. The radiation therapy can also be used to treat keloid scars by reducing the scar size, and by preventing its recurrence [45].

In short, while treating the acne scars, the Ice Pick ones may be treated with punch excision, while the rolling and boxcar types can be treated with various methods such as dermal fillers, chemical peels, or micro-needling. Atrophic surgical scars can be treated with fractional laser therapy, dermal fillers, micro-needling, or surgical scar revision. Table 2 summarizes the general treatment methods for the scar.

Table 2. General treatment methods for scars.

Treatment Option	Description	Reference
Topical treatments	Creams, gels, and silicone sheets can help improve the appearance of scars by reducing redness, flattening the scar, and improving texture.	[58]
Injections	Corticosteroid injections can help reduce inflammation and flatten hypertrophic and keloid scars.	[59]
Surgery	Surgical excision to remove hypertrophic and keloid scars, followed by suturing the wound closed.	[60]
Laser therapy	Laser therapy reduces redness, flattens the scar, improves texture, and stimulates collagen production to improve the skin's overall appearance.	[61]
Cryotherapy	Freezing the scar tissue to reduce inflammation and flatten the scar.	[62]
Pressure therapy	They are applying pressure to the scar using a special bandage or	[63]

	dressing to reduce inflammation and flatten the scar.	
Radiation therapy	They were used to treat keloid scars by reducing the size of the scar and preventing its recurrence.	[64]
Punch excision	Surgical treatment for Ice Pick scars involves excising the scar and allowing it to heal.	[65]
Fractional laser therapy	Laser therapy to improve colour, texture, thickness of atrophic surgical scars.	[66]

5. Advanced Applications of Electrospun Nanofibers in Scar Management

5.1. Electrospinning

Electrospinning is a process driven by high voltage that utilizes electro-hydrodynamic principles to generate fibers from polymeric solutions [67]. The application of high voltage onto a liquid droplet results in both its electrification, and the jet production which elongates and stretches to form fibers [68]. The resultant fibers exhibit diameters ranging from nms to several μms [69]. The primary advantage of the electrospinning depends on its versatility, which enables the fabrication of fibers with diverse configurations, and structures [70].

A typical electrospinning apparatus comprises three primary components [71].

- i. High-voltage power supply: This generates the electric field required for fiber formation.
- ii. Spinneret (metallic needle) – Directs the polymer droplet for jet formation.
- iii. Grounded collector: Collects spun fibers in the form of a non-woven mat.
- iv. The collector can assume various forms, including flat plates, spinning drums, or rotating discs.

The fundamental mechanism of electrospinning can be elucidated by considering a charged droplet of a conductive liquid. When placed in a vacuum, the droplet experiences two opposing forces:[72]

- i. Electrostatic repulsion – Tends to disrupt droplet integrity.
- ii. Surface tension: The spherical shape of the droplet was maintained.

As the voltage is applied to the droplet at the spinneret tip, the droplet elongates into a conical shape known as the "Taylor cone." Then, the droplet generates a stream that is directed towards the collector when the electrostatic force exceeds its surface tension. This liquid can be a polymer melt, a solution, or an emulsion. Solid fibers are formed as the polymer cools down, or as the solvent evaporates during the jet's trajectory from the Taylor cone to the collector, resulting in the deposition of fibers on the collector [73]. The electrospinning can be categorized on the basis of its setup as shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Electrospinning categorisation based on the setup used

This versatile technique can produce fibers with tailored properties for diverse applications, rendering it a critical method in the fields of both nanotechnology and materials science.

5.2. Needle-based electrospinning

During needle electrospinning, a spinneret analogous to a needle is used, and the characteristic cone shape is formed at the needle tip when subjected to an electric field [26].

5.2.1. Single nozzle electrospinning

Here, the fundamental electrospinning configuration employs a single needle as the spinneret, as shown in Fig. 4. This arrangement facilitates the production of individual nanofibers with controlled diameters and orientations. However, the single-needle electrospinning has limitations in terms of production rate, and the scalability for industrial applications [28]. To address these constraints, researchers have developed various modifications along with the basic configuration, including the multi-needle systems and the needleless electrospinning techniques. During this procedure, an equivalent voltage is applied to both solutions, and the resultant fiber typically gets separated due to repulsive forces between two liquids [29].

Fig. 4. Schematic design of the needle-based electrospinning setup

5.2.2. Coaxial electrospinning

The coaxial electrospinning uses a coaxial needle comprised of two concentric hollow needles to generate a coaxially electrified jet. The conventional method for constructing a coaxial needle involves inserting a smaller inner needle into a large outer needle in a coaxial configuration. Here, two syringe pumps are employed to fill both the outer and inner needles with separate solutions, enabling the independent flow rate control [30]. When subjected to an external electric field at the coaxial needle exit, the shell solution encapsulates the core solution, forming a compound Taylor cone, and subsequently ejecting a coaxial jet as shown in Fig. 5. The successful fabrication of core-shell nanofibers is contingent upon several factors, including both the inner and outer solution characteristics and the electrospinning parameters. Specifically, the inner and outer solutions must possess appropriate viscosities to maintain a consistent jet flow.

Additionally, the precise control of the two solutions' flow rates is crucial to ensure the complete encapsulation of the inner solution by the outer solution. Here, the modulation of these flow rates also allows the modification of both the nanofiber diameter and the shell thickness [31].

Fig. 5. Schematic design of the coaxial electrospinning setup

The coaxial electrospinning provides enhanced control over nanofiber compositions for diverse applications, and facilitates the production of nanofibers from unspinnable liquids by utilizing them as the inner fluid regulated by an outer fluid. Hollow nanofibers with a customizable wall thickness can be fabricated through selective elimination of the core from the spun core-shell nanofibers, as well [74]. The core-shell structure of coaxially electrospun fibers presents opportunities for the development of multifunctional materials through the incorporation of various functional components into such concentric structures' both compounds [75].

5.2.3. Tri-axial electrospinning

A trilayer spinneret in a triaxial electrospinning apparatus, which incorporates three nested metal capillaries is illustrated in Fig. 6. This technique is frequently employed to generate a three-layered structure, typically comprising a drug-infused core, hydrophobic middle section, and a hydrophilic exterior layer. A significant challenge in producing high-quality multicompartiment fibers is preventing the mixing of spinning solutions. To accomplish this, the as-used solutions must be either immiscible or get evaporated at identical rates. If one solution evaporates faster than the others, all the compartments may separate, thereby compromising the structure of the targeted fiber. Here, the spinneret design is crucial for maintaining the fiber integrity, as it must be tailored to specific application requirements [34].

Fig. 6. Schematic design of the tri-axial electrospinning setup

A well-engineered spinneret can regulate the fluid behavior under an electric field, and serve as the template to form the desired nanofiber structures. The initial demonstration of triaxial electrospinning utilized a combination of ethanol, lignin, and glycerin arranged from the outermost layer to the innermost layer. Here, ethanol was employed to prevent Taylor cone's solidification, and the glycerin served as the template fluid. This pioneering approach established the foundation for the development of intricate fiber architectures for various applications [76].

5.2.4. Multichannel electrospinning

The fundamental configuration for multichannel electrospinning comprises the placement of three metal capillaries at the vertices of an equilateral triangle within a syringe, as illustrated in the schematic representation in Fig. 7. This arrangement facilitated the fabrication of complex fiber structures. One of the initial demonstrations of this technique was the introduction of a multifluid compound jet electrospinning method, which enabled the expeditious and efficient production of biomimetic hierarchical multichannel microtubes [77].

Fig. 7. The multichannel spinneret

In this approach, multiaxial electrospinning was utilized to develop a biomimetic system by employing multiple inner paraffin oil channels within a titanium isopropoxide solution. Here, the organic components were subsequently removed to form multilayer channels that emulated the natural structures. This methodology demonstrates the multichannel electrospinning's potential in fabricating intricate fiber architectures for advanced applications [78].

5.3. Needle-free electrospinning

To tackle the limitations of conventional needle-based electrospinning, in terms of productivity and scalability, needle-free electrospinning methodologies have been developed and refined [38]. This technique was pioneered by Jirsak et al. at the Technical University of Liberec in the early 2000s [39]. Their primary objective was to overcome the low production rates of needle-based systems, which constrain the large-scale manufacturing of nanofibers. This system involves the generation of multiple cones without the need of either a needle or a small open structure. The process of jet formation in this methodology is based on self-organizing, occurring on an unconfined liquid surface, and is not driven by the capillary action. Instead, it relies on an external agitation force to concentrate the electric field on the free liquid surface, and then intensifying it up to the required level to initiate the Taylor cone [40]. In Fig. 8, the schematic of a needle-free electrospinning setup is shown. In this configuration, the polymer solution is dispensed onto a rotating or vibrating pedestal, while the control pump regulates the solution flow. The high voltage is applied to the pedestal, generating multiple jets of fibers from the polymer solution, which are subsequently collected on the collector surface. This design eliminates the need of a traditional spinneret, thus enabling both higher productivity and large-scale nanofiber production [41].

This innovative approach facilitates higher throughput and scalability than that of traditional needle-based electrospinning techniques. The absence of needle eliminates issues such as clogging, and enables the use of more viscous polymeric solutions. Furthermore, the needle-free electrospinning offers greater flexibility in terms of fiber production since multiple jets can be generated simultaneously from a single liquid surface [42, 43].

Fig. 8. The needle-free electrospinning setup

The primary objective of the needle-free electrospinning is to facilitate the large-scale production of nanofibers by eliminating the requirement for individual nozzles or needles. In contrast to the utilization of a spinneret for fiber ejection from a single point, in needle-free electrospinning, a rotating or vibrating surface (such as a wire, disc, or roller) that concurrently generates multiple jets of a polymer solution, is employed. This approach substantially enhances the throughput and enables the continuous production of nanofiber mats [79].

5.4. Melt electrospinning

Melt electrospinning eliminates the requirement for solvent removal and recycling, thereby addressing the environmental and toxicity concerns associated with solvent utilization. In this process, the polymer is melted and is introduced into a capillary tube. The entire operation must be conducted under vacuum, thereby necessitating the enclosure of a capillary tube, the trajectory of the charged melt fluid jet, and a metal collector [45].

One advantage of the melt electrospinning is the production of highly uniform fibers with minimal variations in diameter. However, this methodology exhibits certain limitations, including the requirement of a specialized equipment, and the relevant challenges presented by both the polymer melt's high viscosity and its low electrical conductivity [80]. Despite its advantages, the melt electrospinning has not achieved widespread adoption or frequent utilization compared to the polymeric solution-based electrospinning. This limited implementation is primarily attributed to the high viscosity, elevated process temperatures, and the challenge of producing fibers in the nanometer range [81].

5.5. Emulsion electrospinning

Emulsion electrospinning involves two distinct methods. The first approach involves the propelling an emulsion through a single nozzle during the electrospinning process, facilitating the rearrangement of the emulsion structure, and resulting in a core-shell fiber analogous to that produced by coaxial electrospinning [82]. The second methodology utilizes multiple nozzles to electrospin an emulsion via generating multiple jets, thereby increasing the production rates while still forming core-shell fibers through structural reorganization [83].

This technique enhances the loading capacity of drug-polymer systems with limited compatibility, such as water-soluble drugs or proteins incorporated into hydrophobic polymers for extended release. In contrast to conventional blending techniques, emulsion electrospinning eliminates the necessity of a solvent capable of simultaneously dissolving both the drug and the polymer. Surfactants and other emulsifying agents are frequently used to encapsulate and to stabilize the drug phase [84].

5.6. Solution electrospinning

Solution electrospinning is the most frequently employed method, in which the polymer to be electrospun is dissolved in an appropriate solvent at an appropriate concentration. The production of nanofibers is predominantly accomplished through solution electrospinning, a technique preferred for its straightforward methodology, and versatility. Here, the selection of both the solvent and the solution concentration is critical, as they directly affects the viscosity, surface tension, and the solution conductivity, which in turn influences the fiber formation and morphology [85].

The as-prepared polymer solution is loaded into a syringe or a capillary tube connected to a high-voltage power supply. An electric field is generated between the needle tip and the grounded collector as the solution is ejected through a fine needle or nozzle. This electric field induces charges in the polymer solution, and causes it to form a Taylor cone at the needle tip. A fine jet is ejected from the cone toward the collector when the electrostatic forces exceed the surface tension of the solution. Along the trajectory, the solvent evaporates and the jet undergoes stretching and whipping motions, resulting in the formation of ultrafine fibers that are deposited on a collector in the form of a non-woven mat [86].

6. Electrospun Nanofiber Treatments for Scar Removal

The versatility of electrospinning allows the formation of fibrous structures from a wide range of both synthetic and natural polymers, potentially facilitating the scar-free wound healing. However, not all polymers can be easily electrospun, as this is influenced by some factors such as viscosity, concentration, and entanglement. For polymers without suitable characteristics for electrospinning, copolymers can be used to enhance the overall mechanical properties. Alginate, a naturally occurring polymer, has a well-established history in wound healing improvement. Its exceptional ability to swell and sustain a moist microenvironment contributes to the healing process [87]. Nevertheless, alginate is lack of the optimal characteristics for electrospinning by itself, primarily due to its insufficient chain entanglement [88].

In a previous study, it is demonstrated that the electrospun collagen/hyaluronic acid nanofibers enhanced skin regeneration by promoting superior cell adhesion and proliferation, while providing both moisturization and structural support to the skin [89]. The incorporation of growth factors and bioactive molecules into such nanofibers could further enhance their regenerative potential. Additionally, the use of crosslinking agents may both improve the mechanical properties and the nanofibers' stability in physiological media. Future studies should focus on optimizing the composition and fabrication parameters of these nanofibers to maximize their efficiency in skin tissue engineering applications. Polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) is a well-regarded polymer for electrospinning and is commonly chosen as a copolymer. PVA is widely utilized in industrial applications, and is preferred in medical field due to its outstanding physical characteristics, ease of processing, and its compatibility with biological systems. Tarun et al. created an electrospun matrix consisting of PVA and sodium alginate [90]. The matrix demonstrated superior water vapor transmission properties, which contributed to the maintenance of a moist environment conducive to wound healing. Furthermore, in-vivo experiments utilizing rats with full-thickness wounds revealed apparent new epithelial growth without any indications of local adverse effects. Indeed, maintaining the wound moisture facilitates the migration of epithelial cells across its surface, thereby promoting effective healing [91].

Chitosan, another example of a naturally occurring polymer, exhibits notable antibacterial and antifungal properties, rendering it advantageous particularly for the application in wound dressings. Ignatova et al. proposed that combining PVA with Q-chitosan (a modified form of chitosan) through a photo-crosslinking electrospinning method would yield a material that is efficacious against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria [92]. The study's results demonstrated that the matrix effectively inhibited the bacterial growth by exhibiting efficacy against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*. However, it is essential to acknowledge that polymers such as chitosan possess certain inherent limitations. For instance, chitosan is characterized by its low solubility, and typically necessitates acidic media, such as acetic acid or trifluoroacetic acid, to dissolve [93,94].

Silk fibroin, a protein synthesized by certain insects such as silkworms, is another naturally occurring polymer recognized for its efficacious wound healing properties. This material is an exemplary candidate for wound repair applications due to its high biocompatibility, anti-inflammatory characteristics, and substantial anti-scarring potential. Consequently, there has been considerable focus on electrospinning silk to create bioactive wound dressings. In one

study, Ju et al. fabricated electrospun silk fibroin nanofibers to treat burn wounds. Their research, conducted on male Sprague-Dawley rats with induced second-degree burn wounds on their dorsal regions, revealed that the silk fibroin-treated skin exhibited significantly lower expression levels of pro-inflammatory cytokine IL-1 α compared to the gauze-treated controls. Additionally, the expression profile of TGF- β 1 in silk fibroin-treated wounds peaked at Day 21 post-wounding before decreasing, whereas the gauze-treated wounds reached their maximum at Day 7. It was also observed in this study that silk fibroin nanofibers promoted rapid collagen formation, which was organized within the wound in a pattern resembling a normal skin rather than a scar tissue [95].

Another previous investigation, entitled as "Exploring the Efficacy of AHA–BHA Infused Nanofiber Skin Masks as a Topical Treatment for Acne Vulgaris", elucidated the potential of nanofiber masks in mitigating inflammation, and promoting skin regeneration, which are crucial factors for both the prevention and treatment of scars [96]. This result is compatible with the one from a previous research about the nanofiber masks, further supporting the use of nanofiber-based materials in dermatological applications for both improved healing outcomes and scar prevention.

7. Electrospun Polymers Enriched with Therapeutics for Scar Treatment

The nanoparticle-based topical treatments have emerged as a promising approach for scar removal due to their unique properties, such as high surface area-to-volume ratio, and the ability to encapsulate drugs, and growth factors [97]. These nanoparticles can target the specific cells involved in wound healing, and modulate their behaviour to promote scar reduction, and tissue regeneration [6]. Some nanoparticles that have shown promise in scar removal include liposomes, solid lipid nanoparticles, and polymeric nanoparticles. These nanoparticles can be loaded with various therapeutic agents, such as anti-inflammatory drugs, growth factors, and antioxidants to further enhance their efficacy [41]. One of the mechanisms by which the nanoparticle-based topical treatments work is through the modulation of the inflammatory response during the wound healing process [21]. By reducing the inflammation, these nanoparticles can prevent excessive scar formation, and can promote tissue regeneration [30]. Additionally, these nanoparticles can enhance both collagen synthesis and remodelling, and thus, further improve the appearance of scars. Several studies have demonstrated the efficacy of nanoparticle-based topical treatments in scar removal. One study demonstrated that polymeric nanoparticles loaded with an anti-inflammatory drug reduced the scar formation, and improved the tissue regeneration in a mouse model [98]. The nanoparticle-based topical treatments are an exciting area of research for both scar removal and tissue regeneration. These treatments have the potential to improve the efficacy of traditional scar treatments by targeting specific cellular, and molecular mechanisms involved in scar formation [99]. Different types of nanoparticles, including liposomes, gold nanoparticles, and quantum dots, have been shown to effectively deliver therapeutic agents onto the scar site, and to promote wound healing through various mechanisms, such as reducing the inflammation, enhancing the collagen production, and promoting the angiogenesis [100]. However, more research is needed to fully understand these treatments' safety, efficacy, and their long-term effects. The nanoparticle-based topical treatments offer a promising avenue for both scar removal and tissue regeneration. Table 3 shows the general overview of the nanoparticles used in scar treatment applications.

Table 3. The most commonly used nanoparticles in scar treatment applications [101].

Nanoparticle	Mechanism of Action	Efficacy
Silver nanoparticles	Antimicrobial properties, promotion of collagen synthesis	Reduces scar size and inflammation
Gold nanoparticles	Anti-inflammatory properties, stimulation of cell growth and differentiation	Reduces scar size and thickness
Zinc oxide nanoparticles	Antioxidant properties, promotion of cell migration and proliferation	Reduces scar formation and improves wound healing
Liposome-encapsulated siRNA nanoparticles	Inhibition of fibroblast activity and collagen production	Reduces hypertrophic scarring and improves wound healing

In a previous review, entitled as "Nano Transdermal Delivery Systems of Herbal Extracts for Dermatological Therapeutics and Skin Care," the application of nanotechnology to enhance the transdermal delivery of herbal extracts for dermatological treatments and skin care was investigated. This study elucidated the improved efficacy of nanotechnology in both facilitating the skin penetration of active compounds, and the therapeutic benefits of herbal extracts along with their reduced adverse effects. These findings are particularly relevant to scar treatment, given to the capacity of nanomaterials to penetrate deeply into the skin, and expedite wound healing through their unique physicochemical properties, and provide a promising method for the integration of natural, and biocompatible substances with advanced delivery mechanisms [10]. The nanomaterials for wound healing have become increasingly popular due to their unique physicochemical, and biological properties [101]. Such nanoparticles have shown potential for promoting the hemostasis, anti-infection, immunoregulation, and proliferation, and they can be used in wound dressings for the sustained delivery of therapeutic agents. Additionally, nanoparticles can detect, and treat bacterial infections by absorbing the light, and transforming it into heat, resulting in bacteria death [102]. However, there are challenges in transforming the nanoparticle-based wound dressings from laboratory experiments to clinical applications, including the reproducibility, toxicity, and the histocompatibility [103]. Animal trials are often used to examine the behaviour of nanoparticle-based wound dressings, but there is still a need for alternative preclinical studies due to the differences between the human, and animal models. Intelligent wound dressings that use nanoparticles or chitosan-based formulations to both detect and treat bacterial infections show promise for the future wound healing processes [104].

7.1. Scar Treatment Through Cell Delivery Using Electrospun Polymers

The use of electrospun polymers as scaffolds for cell delivery presents a promising approach for scar treatment. These nanofibrous structures mimic the extracellular matrix, and provide an ideal environment for cell adhesion, proliferation, and differentiation. By incorporating stem cells or growth factors into electrospun polymer scaffolds, researchers aim to enhance the tissue regeneration, and to minimize scar formation in various wound healing applications [105].

In a previous investigation, entitled as "Pullulan/Collagen Scaffolds Promote Chronic Wound Healing via Mesenchymal Stem Cells," it was observed that the composite scaffolds comprised of Pullulan and Collagen enhanced the cell viability, reduced the cell mortality, and facilitated the tissue regeneration. These properties are particularly significant in treatment of scars, as they possess the potential both to promote healthy cutaneous regeneration, and to mitigate the formation of fibrotic tissue [106].

Multiple studies have investigated the utilization of cellular therapy to promote wound healing, and to minimize the scar formation. However, the conventional methodology for this research typically involves direct cell injection, which proves to be highly inefficient and results in substantial cell death due to the shear forces experienced within the injection needle [106, 107].

In a comparable investigation, Li et al. demonstrated that mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs) incorporated into a three-dimensional graphene foam reduced the scar tissue formation. Here, the foam induced an increase in both the vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF), and the basic fibroblast growth factor (bFGF), promoting enhanced blood vessel formation. Furthermore, it elevated the levels of transforming growth factor beta 3 (TGF- β 3), which inhibits scarring. The researchers evaluated the MSC-loaded foams in-vivo by utilizing a full-thickness wound model in wild-type rats. Compared to untreated or without foam load control groups, the MSC-containing foam significantly accelerated the wound closure commencing from day 3 post-injury. This trend persisted consistently until the study's conclusion at 14 days post-wounding [108].

The accelerated wound closure observed with the MSC-containing foam suggests a synergistic effect between the scaffold and the stem cells. This combination likely creates an optimal microenvironment for the tissue regeneration, promoting rapid healing and reducing the complications' risk. Additionally, the sustained improvement in wound closure throughout the study period indicates both the potential for long-term benefits and reduced recovery times for patients with severe wounds or chronic ulcers.

8. Biocompatibility and Safety Considerations of Nanotechnology-Based Scar Removal

Nanotechnology has significantly shifted wound healing and scar removal [97] since the nanotechnology-based approaches have revolutionized the treatment of wounds, and scars by providing faster healing, and better cosmetic outcomes. However, the biocompatibility, and the safety of these nanotechnology-based approaches still remains a concern. One of the primary concerns is the potential toxicity of nanoparticles (NPs) used in wound healing, and scar removal. Some studies have shown that NPs can cause damage to cells and tissues, leading to inflammation, and oxidative stress. However, the toxicity of NPs depends on their size, shape, and their surface properties [109]. The biodistribution of NPs in the body is another concern since NPs can accumulate in organs and tissues, leading to long-term adverse effects. The accumulation of NPs in the liver, lungs, and spleen has been reported in some studies. However, more research is still needed to fully understand both the biodistribution and the potential toxicity of NPs [110]. The immune response to NPs is also another concern since the immune system can recognize NPs as foreign particles, and generate an immune response against them that lead to inflammation, and tissue damage, depending on their size, shape, and their surface properties [111].

The potential of NPs to induce genotoxicity, and mutagenesis is also a concern. Some studies have shown that NPs can damage DNA, and lead to mutations depending on their size, shape, and their surface properties [89, 112]. The biodegradability of NPs is also an important consideration for their safety. The NPs that are not biodegradable can accumulate in the body, leading to long-term adverse effects [113]. Therefore, it is essential to develop biodegradable NPs that can be safely eliminated from the body. Additionally, the interaction of NPs with other drugs or chemicals is another concern [114], since NPs can interact with other drugs or

chemicals, leading to unexpected toxicity or adverse effects. Therefore, it is essential to consider the potential interactions of NPs with other drugs or chemicals when developing a nanotechnology-based approach for wound healing, and scar removal. The potential for NPs to enter the bloodstream is also a concern since NPs can enter the bloodstream, and travel to other body parts, leading to systemic toxicity. Therefore, it is essential to develop NPs that can be localized on the site of the wound or scar. The potential for NPs to cause allergic reactions is another concern [115] since NPs can induce allergic reactions in some individuals, leading to inflammation, and tissue damage. Therefore, it is essential to consider the potential for NPs to cause allergic reactions when developing a nanotechnology-based approach for wound healing, and scar removal [57,106]. The long-term effects of NPs on the environment are also another concern since NPs can enter the environment through wastewater, leading to potential ecological damage. Therefore, it is essential to develop biodegradable NPs that do not have adverse effects on the environment. The regulatory approval of nanotechnology-based approaches for wound healing, and scar removal is also a concern, and thus, both the safety and efficacy of these approaches must be demonstrated through rigorous pre-/clinical trials before the regulatory approval is obtained.

The biocompatibility and the safety of nanotechnology-based approaches for wound healing, and scar removal still remains a concern since the potential toxicity, biodistribution, immune response, genotoxicity, mutagenesis, biodegradability, interactions with other drugs or chemicals, and the potential for systemic toxicity and allergic reactions, the long-term environmental effects, the regulatory effects, and the regulatory approval are all crucial factors to be considered while both developing and evaluating new medical treatments or substances. Understanding these aspects helps to ensure the safety, and efficacy of the new therapies, to minimize adverse side effects, and to protect both human health, and the environment. Therefore, it is essential to conduct rigorous research, and development to ensure the safety and the efficacy of these approaches.

9. Conclusions

This review explores the recent advances in electrospun nanotechnology for scar management, by focusing on fabrication techniques, therapeutic applications, and safety considerations. Various electrospinning methods, including the needle-based, needleless, melt, emulsion, and solution-based electrospinning are discussed in details via highlighting their advantages and limitations. Incorporating the therapeutic agents into electrospun nanofibers has shown promise in both promoting wound healing and reducing the scar formation. However, the biocompatibility and the safety of these nanomaterials still remains a concern, and necessitates rigorous research to ensure their long-term safety and efficacy. The potential toxicity, biodistribution, immune response, and regulatory aspects of the nanotechnology-based scar treatments are examined in a critical manner. Despite the challenges, the future perspectives of the electrospun nanotechnology in scar management are promising, with the potential both to revolutionize the wound care and to improve patient outcomes.

Author Contributions:

Funding: Not applicable.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Acknowledgments: We extend our heartfelt appreciation to Bahattin Güner for his crucial support throughout this endeavor. His guidance, genuine enthusiasm, and knowledge were instrumental in the successful execution of the experiments. We are grateful for his ongoing encouragement and valuable input.

Declaration of Competing Interest: An earlier version of this study was published as a preprint on www.preprints.org server. The DOI number is as follows ...

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